

The Use Of High-Performance Thermoplastic Composites For Structural Aerospace Applications - Status And Outlook

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ABSTRACT

Due to a demand for improvements in damage tolerance and cost-effective manufacturing of aerospace structures, thermoplastic matrix composites are regarded as a promising alternative to thermoset materials. Based on the in-house experience, especially with carbon fibre reinforced PEEK, this paper tries to review critically the reasons of the limited use of thermoplastic composites in aerospace applications up to now. On the one hand, thermoplastic composites show specific advantages in material properties, e.g. low moisture pick up, good fracture toughness, and also in processing like press consolidation and hot formability of pre-consolidated plates. On the other hand, high material costs as well as from the thermosets different processing conditions (i.e. high temperature) and equipment needed have prevented thermoplastic composites from being used more intensively in primary aircraft structures up to now.

1. INTRODUCTION

The appearance of a thermoplastic structural composite involving continuous carbon fibre tapes preimpregnated with PEEK resin started about ten years ago and created extensive interest in the aerospace industry. At that time, it became obvious that the standard fibre reinforced composite materials based on thermosetting epoxy resins showed two severe drawbacks: poor resistance to moisture and low damage tolerance, which seemed to limit further applications of these materials. The use of thermoplastic composites promised to solve these problems and reduce the manufacturing costs of composite aircraft components. Since that time an enormous amount of literature in this field has been published (1-5) dealing with material properties, processing and first applications in the aerospace area. The analysis of the available literature, however, now demonstrates that the optimistic visions of the respective suppliers of thermoplastic composites with regard to the use of these materials in the aerospace industry have not taken place and that there are only very few applications of advanced thermoplastic composites in which development is advanced enough to warrant flight testing or even full commercial use (6-8). The aim of this paper is to present data evaluated at DASA on mechanical properties and processing relevant to aerospace requirements of thermoplastic composites focussing on carbon fibre reinforced PEEK. Based on these results and considering the boundary conditions with regard to manufacturing and volume of products within the aerospace industry the penetration potential of thermoplastic composites into this area will be discussed.

2. TECHNICAL DEMANDS ON MATRIX SYSTEMS FOR USE IN ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

The operational requirements for a structural material in aerospace applications are determined by two sets of technical factors:

- those imposed by the environment (i. e. temperature, moisture, solvent media)
- those determined by function (i. e. stiffness, strength, coefficient of thermal expansion)

The driving force for the use of composite materials is the attainment of high specific properties, i. e. stiffness and strength per unit weight, which requires, apart from the choice of maximum fibre performance, polymer systems with high stiffness and yield strength to control fiber buckling in the compressive mode and interfacial adhesion between fibres together with good shear strength to promote load transfer. Thermosetting polymer systems, mainly epoxy resins, have shown to fulfill to a high degree these requirements, although the disadvantages of limited toughness and time-consuming cure cycles have become obvious especially in the last several years. Therefore, the appearance of structural composites based on advanced thermoplastic matrices seemed to be an attractive alternative. Mainly PEEK, PPS and PEI are used as matrices in commercially available thermoplastic prepregs intended for structural applications. Out of these resins polyetheretherketone (PEEK) has obtained by far the most interest because it offers from the technical point of view the best overall performance. This is reflected in the fact that in most publications this resin type is considered as a serious contender for commercial use in aerospace applications. Also in our company most of the work in the area of thermoplastic composites is devoted to "C"-Prepregs" with PEEK, sold under the tradename APC2 by ICI. In the following comments, we shall therefore refer mainly to the test results obtained by the use of this system.

3. PROPERTIES OF ADVANCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

Due to the different chemical nature of thermoplastics in comparison to thermoset resins thermoplastics exhibit characteristic properties which result also in the case of use as long-fibre reinforced materials in a balance of properties differing in some respect from the "conventional" thermoset composites. Figure 1 shows in a generalized table the advantages and disadvantages of thermoplastic composites taken with the example of PEEK as a matrix.

With regard to mechanical performance it can be stated that PEEK based thermoplastic composites exhibit properties which are in many areas superior to those of thermoset materials. It is well known that moisture pick-up has a detrimental effect on the so-called "hot-wet" performance of thermoset composites. As is well known, PEEK based composites show a significantly reduced moisture absorption, even in comparison to recently developed new thermoset systems. As was demonstrated, this feature translates in a low decrease in mechanical performance due to humidity effects.

Another topic of interest is the question of maximum continuous service temperature of thermoplastic composites in structural applications. To this end, investigations have been performed to assess the mechanical performance (compression and transverse tensile strength) at room temperature and at 200°C involving different thermoplastic and BMI based carbon fibre composites. The results of these tests are graphically represented in Figures 2 and 3. Whereas in compression strength a significantly lower performance level of all thermoplastic systems is found, the values of the transverse tensile strength reflecting the adhesion and matrix

properties differ only slightly between these two classes of material with the exception of the PEEK composite (APC2) which exhibits by far the best performance.

One of the major issues in the area of advanced composites is the evaluation of damage tolerance. For the investigation of this important material feature, preference is given in the aircraft industry to a test procedure in which damage is produced in a multidirectional laminate test specimen by applying a range of impact energy levels in a falling drop-weight testing device and then determining this effect with regard to formation of invisible delaminations and reduction of compression strength. Figure 4 shows the impact behaviour of carbon fibre reinforced composites with different epoxy matrices and a thermoplastic matrix (PEEK). Considerable progress has been achieved in thermosets by means of toughening modifications in the resin structure as demonstrated by these experimental results. However, it should be mentioned that thermoplastic composites have some advantages in detectability of impact damages, since impact events--as in metals--lead in most cases to visible deformations.

In summary, it can be stated that PEEK based composites fulfill all aerospace requirements with regard to mechanical performance with slight deficiencies in compression strength. However, the claimed lead function in toughness properties is, due to the advent of newly developed tough thermosets, no longer a major driving force for the use of thermoplastic composites.

4. PROCESSING THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

For the production of advanced fibre reinforced thermoset composite components in the aerospace industry, autoclaves are mainly used in which the curing reaction takes place under controlled conditions of temperature and pressure. It is obvious that such a process is time consuming and expensive to operate. Referring to this situation it is claimed by the respective suppliers of thermoplastic composites that important benefits with regard to cost-effective manufacture of composite structures can be realized. What is the current manufacturing situation for thermoplastics?

Some basic characteristics of processing conditions of thermoplastic and thermoset prepreps are compared in Figure 5. The most important issue for the evaluation of the cost-effectiveness of the manufacturing process is the cycle time required. In Figure 6 different processing methods for continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites are enumerated and estimated qualitatively with regard to cycle times and producibility of components with respect to shape and geometry. It can be seen from this table that only the thermoforming process has a high potential for a cost-effective, high-speed manufacturing process. This is validated by Figure 7, where typical processing cycles for thick wall (ca. 2 - 10 mm) structural aerospace components applying different processes and materials are shown. The figure demonstrates that the autoclave option for processing thermoplastic composites requires lengthy heat-up and cool-down periods due to the high processing temperature needed, which results only in a marginal reduction in total processing time in comparison to epoxy based composites. The advantage of using press processing cannot be realized in many aerospace applications due to configuration and size constraints and high tooling costs required in the case of a press. In general, it must be mentioned that auxiliary materials like sealants and bagging films needed in the case of vacuum processing give rise to problems for high temperature thermoplastic processing. Therefore only expensive materials like polyimide films and special sealants fulfill the performance required in these applications.

The users of thermoplastic prepreps have to face the fact that these materials tend to be very stiff and difficult to manipulate. Especially shaping parts with significant double curvature from thermoplastic prepreps require special care and needs considerable labour-intensive

manipulation to avoid wrinkles and creases. To minimize these problems associated with thermoplastic prepregs non-impregnated thermoplastic preforms in a large variety of physical forms e.g. commingled and cowoven fabrics have been supplied in the last years by the respective composite manufacturers. An overview of the advantages and drawbacks of these materials is given in Figure 8. Due to the textile processability of thermoplastic fibers, special woven or braided preforms featuring e.g. a 3-D-reinforcement can be realized, which can be easily consolidated to laminates requiring no additional resin injection (9-11).

5. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

It was about 10 years ago that continuous carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic structural composites were introduced on the market creating high interest in the aerospace industry to use these materials as alternatives to the well established thermoset composites. It was argued by the respective suppliers that this new class of material held the promise of being tougher than the state of the art epoxies and greatly reducing the fabrication costs associated with composite parts. The potential for rapid and cost-effective processing resulted in a high number of research and developmental programmes to demonstrate these potential benefits. The results of these investigations are by far not as positive as was expected. This is shown by the fact that there are only very limited structural aircraft applications of advanced thermoplastic composites, being flight tested in small number, which have a chance to go in production. What are the reasons for this?

A key factor represents the question of cost competitiveness. There is no doubt that for high volume applications like in the automotive field thermoplastics are advantageous. However, in nearly all structural aerospace applications the production number is very limited. Moreover, most of the parts are complexly shaped and may vary considerably in thickness locally. Due to these geometric conditions and quality requirements, autoclave processing is in many cases the only possible process route to go. Compared to the thermoset processing this means higher costs due to

- autoclave capable of operating at higher temperatures
- more expensive tooling
- more expensive auxiliary materials

Furthermore, the partly significantly higher material costs of thermoplastic composites have to be taken into account.

As no real production experience with thermoplastic composites is available, the prediction of labour costs associated with these processes is difficult to document accurately. Although a number of studies are available in the literature (12, 13) no clear conclusions can be drawn at this moment. What can be stated is that the relative cost competitiveness of thermoplastic and thermosetting composites will depend strongly on the shape of the part, the manufacturing technique and the initial starting form of the thermoplastic. There is no doubt that for simple parts and non-autoclave manufacturing processes, thermoplastics are clearly competitive as they allow a wider range of labour efficient manufacturing routes to be used. In other cases, and this represents the majority in aerospace applications, the competitiveness of thermoplastic composites is still in doubt. Future efforts must be concentrated on automation of the processes involved. Maybe the penetration of composites applications into industries outside aerospace, namely automotive requiring high-volume manufacturing will lead to price-competitive processes which will then stimulate the use of thermoplastic composites in aerospace applications.

6. References

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Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high fracture toughness • low moisture pick-up • unlimited storage capability • potential for short processing cycles • good temperature capability • repairability (post forming) • good potential for recycling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • high price • high processing temperature • high melt viscosity • no "tack" • limited experience on long-term behavior • stiff, boardy material (as "prepreg")

Figure 1. Assessment of advantages and drawbacks of long-fibre reinforced thermoplastics (PEEK)

Figure 2: Comparison of the ud-compression strength of different thermoplastic and thermoset composites

Figure 3: Comparison of the transverse tensile strength of different thermoplastic and thermoset composites

Figure 4: Invisible damage areas of different CFRP-systems after impact loading

Processing Conditions	Prepreg with	
	Thermoplastic Matrix (PEEK)	Thermoset Matrix (Epoxy Resin)
laying of prepreg	difficult time consuming non drapeable, no "tack"	time consuming can be automated
temperature	385°C	up to 180°C
pressure	4 to 10 bar	4 to 7 bar
vacuum	not necessary	necessary
curing cycles (cycle time)	depends on the processing method	long (some hours)
postcuring	no	partly necessary
subsequent formability	possible	not possible
processing equipment	press (autoclave)	autoclave

Figure 5. Comparison of the processing of thermoplastic and thermosetting prepreps

Processes	Processing cycle	Components
thermoforming	short	thin wall parts
compression moulding	medium	simple shaped parts
diaphragma forming	long	complex shaped parts
autoclave processing	long	complex shaped parts
filament winding	medium	axially symmetrical parts
pultrusion	continuous	different shaped profiles

Figure 6. Processing methods for thermoplastic composites

Figure 7: Comparison of typical processing times for thermoplastic and thermoset composites

Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • good drape properties • higher flexibility with respect to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - combination of materials - orientation of fibres - style of weaving • producibility of complex style of preforms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lower fibre efficiency • longer consolidation time • more critical handling

Figure 8. Assessment of advantages and drawbacks of non-impregnated thermoplastic preforms (commingled, cowoven)